

An iterative method for inverse source bi-parabolic equation

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Abstract

In this paper, we consider the problem of finding the source function for bi-parabolic equation. First, the problem is severely ill-posed in the sense of Hadamard. After that, we also give a regularized solution and consider the convergence between the regularized solution and the sought solution by an iterative method, under a priori parameter choice rule, and under a posteriori parameter choice rule, respectively.

Keywords: conformable derivative, Fourier truncation method, inverse source problem, inverse initial problem, regularization, Sobolev embeddings.

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1. Introduction

In this paper, we consider an inverse source problem of determining the space dependent source term $f(x)$ for the following bi-parabolic equation with Ω be a bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^2 with the sufficiently smooth

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boundary $\partial\Omega$.

$$\begin{cases} u_{tt}(x, t) + 2\Delta u_t(x, t) + \Delta^2 u(x, t) = \Phi(t)f(x), & (x, t) \in \Omega \times (0, T), \\ u_t(x, 0) = 0, & (x) \in \partial\Omega, t \in (0, T], \\ u|_{\partial\Omega} = \Delta u|_{\partial\Omega} = 0, & x \in \Omega, \\ u(x, 0) = u_0(x), & x \in \Omega, \\ \rho \int_0^T u(x, t) dt = g(x), & x \in \Omega. \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

Our main aim in this article is to recover the source function f from the given data Φ , u_0 and g . The problem (1.1) is severely ill-posed in the sense of Hadamard; the problem that either has no solutions in the desired class, or has many (two or more) solutions, or the solution procedure is unstable (i.e., arbitrarily small errors in the measurement data φ may lead to indefinitely large errors in the solutions). Most difficulties in solving ill-posed problems are caused by solution instability. To overcome this instability character, regularization methods are required.

In fact, the exact data can be measured, there will be measurement errors, and we thus would have as data function Φ^ϵ in $L^\infty(0, T)$ for which

$$\|u_0 - u_{0,\epsilon}\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \epsilon, \quad \|g_\epsilon - g\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \epsilon, \quad \|\Phi^\epsilon - \Phi\|_{L^\infty(0,T)} \leq \epsilon, \quad (1.2)$$

where the constant $\epsilon > 0$ represents a noised data.

In general, we can divide the source into three classes according to the dependent variables: time-dependent source, spatially dependent source. For the time-dependent source, one can refer to [16]-[17] for stability estimation and computational methods on the bounded domain and refer to [18]-[19] for the above regularization methods. Unlimited domains. For a space-dependent source, we refer to readers of [14, 10, 7, 11, 13, 6]. In this paper, we will extend the iterative method developed in [15] to solve the inverse source problem. Heat transfer theory is applied by bi-parabolic equations, since heat conduction processes cannot be described exactly by the classical parabolic equation [5, 8, 4, 1, 2], so many models have been proposed to describe this process, they include the dipole model proposed in [4], and the regularization method applied in this section is iterative method, see [9, 20].

The outline of the rest of this article is as follows. In Section 2, we will show that the preliminary results. In Section 3, we have shown the solution of the problem (1.1), the ill-posedness in the sense of Hadamard, and the conditional stability of source term f . In section 4, we apply the iterative regularization method for finding an approximate solution and show the convergent rate between the exact solution and the its approximation under a priori parameter choice rule and under a posteriori parameter choice rule. Finally, a conclusion is attached to this article.

2. Preliminary results

Throughout this paper \mathcal{K} denotes a complex separable Hilbert space endowed with the inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ and the norm $\| \cdot \|$, $\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{K})$ stands for the Banach algebra of bounded linear operators on \mathcal{J} . Let \mathcal{J} be a real Hilbert space, and let $\mathcal{J} : \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{A}) \subset \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ be a linear, positive-definite, self-adjoint operator with compact inverse on \mathcal{J} . \mathcal{A} has an orthonormal basis of eigenvectors $e_m \subset \mathcal{J}$ with real eigenvalues $\lambda_m \in \mathbb{R}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}e_m(x) &= \lambda_m e_m(x), \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad \langle e_m, e_n \rangle = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } m = n, \\ 0, & \text{if } m \neq n. \end{cases} \\ \text{and } 0 < \lambda_1 &\leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \text{ with } \lambda_m \rightarrow \infty \text{ for } m \rightarrow \infty, \end{aligned} \quad (2.1)$$

and the corresponding eigenelements e_n which form an orthonormal basis in \mathcal{J} .

Definition 2.1. The Hilbert scale space \mathbb{H}^s , ($s > 0$) defined by

$$\mathbb{H}^s(\Omega) := \left\{ f \in L^2(\Omega) : \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_m^2)^s \langle f, e_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \leq \infty \right\}, \tag{2.2}$$

with the norm

$$\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^s(\Omega)}^2 = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_m^2)^s |\langle f, e_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}|^2 < \infty. \tag{2.3}$$

Lemma 2.2. Let $\lambda_m > \lambda_1 > 0$, $\forall m \geq 1$ and $\tau \in [0, T]$, we obtain

$$\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)}(t-\tau)d\tau = \frac{(1 - (1 + t\lambda_m)e^{-\lambda_m t})}{\lambda_m^2}. \tag{2.4}$$

Lemma 2.3. [12] Assume that there exist positive constants $\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2$ such that $\mathcal{A}_1 \leq |\Phi(t)| \leq \mathcal{A}_2 \forall t \in [0, T]$, let choose $\epsilon \in (0, \frac{\mathcal{A}_1}{2})$, we obtain

$$\frac{\mathcal{A}_1}{2} \leq |\Phi_\epsilon(t)| \leq \mathcal{A}(\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2), \quad \mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2) = \mathcal{A}_1 + \frac{\mathcal{A}_2}{2}. \tag{2.5}$$

Proof. The proof of the Lemma in [12]. □

Lemma 2.4. [3] For $0 < \lambda < 1$, defining $\zeta_\alpha(\lambda) = \sum_{j=0}^{\alpha-1} (1-\lambda)^j$ and

$\theta_\alpha(\lambda) = 1 - \lambda\zeta_\alpha(\lambda) = (1-\lambda)^\alpha$, there hold

$$\zeta_\alpha(\lambda)\lambda^v \leq \alpha^{1-v}, \quad \forall 0 \leq v \leq 1, \quad \theta_\alpha(\lambda)\lambda^\xi \leq \Theta_\xi(\alpha+1)^{-\xi}, \tag{2.6}$$

where $\Theta_\xi = \begin{cases} 1, & 0 \leq \xi \leq 1, \\ \xi^\xi, & \xi > 1. \end{cases}$

3. Regularization and error estimate for unknown source (1.1)

In this section, we consider the following problem

$$\begin{cases} u''(t) + 2\mathcal{A}u'(t) + \mathcal{A}^2u(t) = F(t), & 0 < t < T, \\ u'(0) = 0, \\ \rho \int_0^T u(t)dt = g. \end{cases} \tag{3.1}$$

First, taking the inner product of both sides of (3.1) with $e_m(x)$, it gives

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d^2}{dt^2} \langle u(t), e_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} + 2\lambda_m \frac{d}{dt} \langle u(t), e_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} + \lambda_m^2 \langle u(t), e_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} = \Phi(t) \langle f, e_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}, & t \in (0, T), \\ \langle u(0), e_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} = u_m(0), \\ \frac{d}{dt} \langle u(0), e_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} = 0, \\ \rho \int_0^T \langle u(t), e_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)} dt = \langle g, e_m \rangle_{L^2(\Omega)}. \end{cases} \tag{3.2}$$

Using the Lagrange constant variable method, we have the following system

$$u_m(t) = (1 + \lambda_m t)e^{-\lambda_m t}u_m(0) + \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m \tau} \Phi(\tau) d\tau\right) t e^{-\lambda_m t} f_m - \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m \tau} \tau \Phi(\tau) d\tau\right) f_m e^{-\lambda_m t}, \quad (3.3)$$

with $u_m(t) = \langle u(t), e_m \rangle$, $f_m = \langle f, e_m \rangle$, $u_m(0) = \langle u(0), e_m \rangle$, and $g_m = \langle g, e_m \rangle$. It gives

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g, e_m \rangle &= \rho \int_0^T \langle u(t), e_m \rangle dt = \rho_2 \langle u(\cdot, 0), e_m \rangle \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_m} (1 - e^{-\lambda_m T}) - T e^{-\lambda_m T} \right) \\ &+ \rho \langle f, e_m \rangle \int_0^T t \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt - \rho \langle f, e_m \rangle \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} \tau \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt. \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

From (3.4), through some basic calculation steps, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \langle g, e_m \rangle &= \rho \langle u(\cdot, 0), e_m \rangle \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_m} (1 - e^{-\lambda_m T}) - T e^{-\lambda_m T} \right) \\ &+ \rho \langle f, e_m \rangle \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t - \tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt. \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

A simple transformation gives

$$\langle f, e_m \rangle = \frac{\langle g, e_m \rangle - \rho \langle u(\cdot, 0), e_m \rangle \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_m} (1 - e^{-\lambda_m T}) - T e^{-\lambda_m T} \right)}{\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t - \tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt}, \quad (3.6)$$

then we obtain the formula of the source function f

$$f(x) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\langle g, e_m \rangle e_m(x) - \rho \langle u(\cdot, 0), e_m \rangle \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_m} (1 - e^{-\lambda_m T}) - T e^{-\lambda_m T} \right) e_m(x)}{\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t - \tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt}. \quad (3.7)$$

From now on, for a shorter, we denote

$$\langle \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(x) = \langle g, e_m \rangle e_m(x) - \rho \langle u(\cdot, 0), e_m \rangle \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_m} (1 - e^{-\lambda_m T}) - T e^{-\lambda_m T} \right) e_m(x). \quad (3.8)$$

Combining (3.7) and (3.8), we can be written

$$f(x) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\langle \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(x)}{\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t - \tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt}. \quad (3.9)$$

3.1. Conditional stability of source term f

Theorem 3.1. Assume that $g \in L^2(\Omega)$ and $u_0 \in L^2(\Omega)$, if $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^{2s}(\Omega)} \leq \mathcal{M}$ for $\mathcal{M} > 0$ then

$$\|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq C(s, M) \|\ell\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^{\frac{s}{s+1}}, \text{ where } C(s, \mathcal{M}) = \left(T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1}\right)^{\frac{-2s}{s+1}} \rho^{-\frac{2s}{s+1}} |\mathcal{A}_1|^{-\frac{2s}{s+1}} \mathcal{M}^{\frac{2}{s+1}}.$$

Proof. Before starting to prove, using the inequality $(a + b)^2 \leq 2a^2 + b^2$, for $a, b \geq 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle \ell, e_m \rangle|^2 &= 2|\langle g, e_m \rangle|^2 + \rho^2 |\langle u(\cdot, 0), e_m \rangle|^2 \left| \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_m} (1 - e^{-\lambda_m T}) - T e^{-\lambda_m T} \right) \right|^2 \\ &\leq 2\|g\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + 2\rho^2 \|u_0\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 (4T^2 + 2T^2 e^{-2\lambda_1 T}). \end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

This implies that

$$\|\ell\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \sqrt{2} \|g\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + \sqrt{2} \rho \|u_0\|_{L^2(\Omega)} (4T^2 + 2T^2 e^{-2\lambda_1 T})^{\frac{1}{2}}. \tag{3.11}$$

Next, from (3.7) and Hölder inequality, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 &= \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left| \frac{\langle \ell, e_m \rangle}{\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt} \right|^2 = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{|\langle \ell, e_m \rangle|^{\frac{2}{s+1}} |\langle \ell, e_m \rangle|^{\frac{2s}{s+1}}}{\left| \rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt \right|^2} \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{|\langle \ell, e_m \rangle|^2}{\left| \rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt \right|^{2s+2}} \right)^{\frac{1}{s+1}} \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} |\langle \ell, e_m \rangle|^2 \right)^{\frac{s}{s+1}} \\ &\leq \left(\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{|\langle f, e_m \rangle|^2}{\left| \rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt \right|^{2s}} \right)^{\frac{1}{s+1}} \|\ell\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^{\frac{2s}{s+1}}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

From (3.12), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt \right|^{2s} &\geq \frac{\rho^{2s} |\mathcal{A}_1|^{2s}}{\lambda_m^{4s}} \left| \int_0^T (1 - (1 + t\lambda_m) e^{-\lambda_m t}) dt \right|^{2s} \\ &\geq \left| T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1} \right|^{2s}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.13}$$

and this inequality leads to

$$\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{|\langle f, e_m \rangle|^2}{\left| \rho \left(\int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt \right) \right|^{2s}} \leq \frac{\left(T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1}\right)^{-2s}}{\rho^{2s} |\mathcal{A}_1|^{2s}} \|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^{2s}(\Omega)}^2. \tag{3.14}$$

Combining (3.12) and (3.14), we get

$$\|f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \leq \left(T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1}\right)^{\frac{-2s}{s+1}} \rho^{-\frac{2s}{s+1}} (\mathcal{A}_1)^{-\frac{2s}{s+1}} \mathcal{M}^{\frac{2}{s+1}} \|\ell\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^{\frac{2s}{s+1}}. \tag{3.15}$$

□

4. Regularization of the inverse source problem by the iterative regularization method

In this section, we propose an iterative method to solve the inverse source problem (3.1). Let $v_\epsilon^\alpha(x, t)$ be the solution of the following problem

$$\begin{cases} v_{\epsilon,tt}^\alpha(x, t) + 2\Delta v_{\epsilon,t}^\alpha(x, t) + \Delta^2 v_\epsilon^\alpha(x, t) = \Phi_\epsilon(t) f_\epsilon^\alpha(x), & (x, t) \in \Omega \times (0, T), \\ v_{\epsilon,t}^\alpha(x, 0) = 0, & (x) \in \partial\Omega, t \in (0, T], \\ v_\epsilon^\alpha(x, 0) = u_0^\alpha(x), & x \in \bar{\Omega}, \\ f_\epsilon^\alpha(x) = f_\epsilon^{\alpha-1}(x) - k \left(\left(\rho \int_0^T v_\epsilon(x, t) dt \right)^{\alpha-1} - \ell_\epsilon(x) \right), & x \in \bar{\Omega}. \end{cases} \tag{4.1}$$

in which α plays the role of regularization parameter and k is an accelerated factor satisfying $0 < k\rho \frac{\mathcal{L}(\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2)T}{\lambda_1^2} < 1$.

1. Next, we will construct the regularized solution $f_\epsilon^{\alpha,k}$ for the inverse source, denoting $\mu_{\epsilon,m} = k\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau)\Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt$ and taking $f_\epsilon^0 = 0$, this implies that $v_\epsilon^\alpha(x, t) = \sum_{m=1}^\infty \langle f_\epsilon^\alpha, e_m \rangle \rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau)\Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt e_m(x)$.

Form the condition f_ϵ^α in the (4.1), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle f_\epsilon^\alpha, e_m \rangle &= \langle f_\epsilon^{\alpha-1}, e_m \rangle - k \left(\langle f_\epsilon^{\alpha-1}, e_m \rangle \rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau)\Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt - \langle \ell_\epsilon, e_m \rangle \right) \\ &= (1 - \mu_{\epsilon,m}) \langle f_\epsilon^{\alpha-1}, e_m \rangle + k \langle \ell_\epsilon, e_m \rangle = (1 - \mu_{\epsilon,m})^\alpha \langle f_\epsilon^0, e_m \rangle + \sum_{j=0}^{\alpha-1} (1 - \mu_{\epsilon,m})^j k \langle \ell_\epsilon, e_m \rangle. \end{aligned} \tag{4.2}$$

Taking $\langle f_\epsilon^0, e_m \rangle = 0$, it gives $\langle f_\epsilon^\alpha, e_m \rangle = \sum_{j=0}^{\alpha-1} (1 - \mu_{\epsilon,m})^j k \langle \ell_\epsilon, e_m \rangle$ and

$$f_\epsilon^\alpha(x) = \sum_{m=1}^\infty \left(\sum_{j=0}^{\alpha-1} (1 - \mu_{\epsilon,m})^j k \langle \ell_\epsilon, e_m \rangle \right) e_m(x) = \sum_{m=1}^\infty \zeta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) k \langle \ell_\epsilon, e_m \rangle e_m(x). \tag{4.3}$$

Similarly, we have $f^\alpha(x) = \sum_{m=1}^\infty \zeta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) k \langle \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(x)$, which allows us to get that

$$\begin{aligned} f_\epsilon^\alpha(x) - f(x) &= f_\epsilon^\alpha(x) - f^\alpha(x) + f^\alpha(x) - f(x) \\ &= \sum_{m=1}^\infty \zeta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) k \langle \ell_\epsilon - \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(x) + \sum_{m=1}^\infty \frac{(-\theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m})) \langle \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(x)}{\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau)\Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.4}$$

4.1. An a priori parameter choice rule

Before going into the main progress proof, we assess the estimate $\|\ell_\epsilon - \ell\|_{L^2(\Omega)}$ as follows :

Lemma 4.1. *Let ℓ be given by (3.8) depends on g and u_0 functions. Similarly, in a similar way we can find the function definition with the couple $(g_\epsilon, u_{0,\epsilon})$ are measured data by (g, u_0) as follows $\langle \ell_\epsilon, e_m \rangle = \langle g_\epsilon, e_m \rangle - \rho \langle u_{0,\epsilon}, e_m \rangle \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_m} (1 - e^{-\lambda_m T}) - T e^{-\lambda_m T} \right)$, denoting $\mathcal{A}_3^2 = (2 + 8\rho^2 T^2 + 4T^2 \rho^2 e^{-2\lambda_1 T})$ then we have*

Proof. Using the inequality $(a + b)^2 \leq 2a^2 + 2b^2, \forall a, b \geq 0$ and the inequality $1 - e^{-x} \leq x, \forall x \geq 0$, it gives

$$\begin{aligned} \|\ell_\epsilon - \ell\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 &= \sum_{m=1}^\infty \left\| \langle g_\epsilon - g, e_m \rangle - \rho \langle u_{0,\epsilon} - u_0, e_m \rangle \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_m} (1 - e^{-\lambda_m T}) - T e^{-\lambda_m T} \right) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \\ &\leq 2 \sum_{m=1}^\infty |\langle g_\epsilon - g, e_m \rangle|^2 + 2\rho^2 \sum_{m=1}^\infty \left\| \langle u_{0,\epsilon} - u_0, e_m \rangle (2T + T e^{-\lambda_1 T}) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 \\ &\leq 2\|g_\epsilon - g\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 + 2\rho^2 \|u_{0,\epsilon} - u_0\|_{L^2(\Omega)}^2 (4T^2 + 2T^2 e^{-2\lambda_1 T}) \leq \epsilon^2 \mathcal{A}_3^2. \end{aligned} \tag{4.5}$$

□

Theorem 4.2. *Suppose that a priori condition (3.1) and the noise assumption (1.2) hold, then if we have*

$$\|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \text{ is of order } \epsilon^{\frac{s}{s+1}}. \tag{4.6}$$

Proof. By the triangle inequality, we know that

$$\|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \underbrace{\|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f^\alpha\|_{L^2(\Omega)}}_{\text{first term}} + \underbrace{\|f^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}}_{\text{second term}} \tag{4.7}$$

Estimation for the first term, using (4.7), (1.2) and part a) of the Lemma 2.4 with $v = 0$, one has

$$\|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f^\alpha\|_{L^2(\Omega)} = \left\| \sum_{m=1}^\infty \zeta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) k \langle \ell_\epsilon - \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(x) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \sup_{m \in \mathbb{N}^*} \zeta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) k \epsilon \mathcal{A}_3 \leq \epsilon \mathcal{A}_3 \alpha k. \tag{4.8}$$

Next, we estimate the second term, using the priori condition $\|f\|_{\mathbb{H}^{2s}} \leq \mathcal{M}$, combining the Lemma 2.4 and by choosing with $\xi = 2s$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|f^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} &= \left\| \sum_{m=1}^\infty \left(-\theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) \right) \left[\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi_\epsilon(\tau) d\tau \right) dt \right]^{-1} \langle \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(x) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &= \left\| \sum_{m=1}^\infty \theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) \langle f, e_m \rangle e_m(x) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} = \left(\sum_{m=1}^\infty \theta_\alpha^2(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) |\langle f, e_m \rangle|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \left(\sum_{m=1}^\infty \frac{\theta_\alpha^2(\mu_{\epsilon,m})}{(\lambda_m^2)^{2s}} (\lambda_m^2)^{2s} |\langle f, e_m \rangle|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \leq \sup_{m \in \mathbb{N}^*} \frac{\theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m})}{\lambda_m^{2s}} \left(\sum_{m=1}^\infty (\lambda_m^2)^{2s} |\langle f, e_m \rangle|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned} \tag{4.9}$$

From (4.9), based on $\mu_{\epsilon,m} = k\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt$ is defined above, and some simple transformations, we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\|f^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &\leq \frac{\mathcal{M}}{\lambda_1^{2s}} \left(\sup_{m \in \mathbb{N}^*} \theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) \left[\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi_\epsilon(\tau) d\tau \right) dt \right]^s \right) \left[\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi_\epsilon(\tau) d\tau \right) dt \right]^{-s} \\ &\leq \frac{\mathcal{M}}{\lambda_1^{2s}} \frac{2^s (T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1})^{-s}}{(k\rho \mathcal{A}_1)^s} \left(\sup_{m \in \mathbb{N}^*} \theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) \left[\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi_\epsilon(\tau) d\tau \right) dt \right]^s \right) \\ &\leq \frac{\mathcal{M}}{\lambda_1^{2s}} \frac{2^s (T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1})^{-s}}{(k\rho \mathcal{A}_1)^s} \sup_{m \in \mathbb{N}^*} \left(\theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) |\mu_{\epsilon,m}|^s \right) \leq Q_1 \theta_s(\alpha + 1)^{-s}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.10}$$

whereby Q_1 is a constant which depends on $\mathcal{M}, \lambda_1, s, T, k, \rho, \mathcal{A}_1$. Combining (4.7) to (4.9), we conclude that

$$\|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \epsilon \mathcal{A}_3 \alpha k + Q_1 \theta_s (\alpha + 1)^{-s}. \tag{4.11}$$

α is chosen by

$$\alpha = \left[\frac{1}{k} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}}{\epsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{s+1}} \right]. \tag{4.12}$$

From (4.8) and (4.11), we conclude that

$$\|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \epsilon^{\frac{s}{s+1}} \mathcal{M}^{\frac{1}{s+1}} (\mathcal{A}_3 + \theta_s Q_2). \tag{4.13}$$

whereby Q_2 is a constant which depends on $\lambda_1, s, T, \rho, \mathcal{A}_1$ and $Q_2 = \frac{\mathcal{M} 2^s (T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1})^{-s}}{\lambda_1^{2s} (\rho \mathcal{A}_1)^s}$. □

4.2. An a posteriori parameter choice rule

In this subsection, we will give an a posteriori as follow:

$$\|\mathcal{S}f_\epsilon^\alpha - \ell_\epsilon\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \kappa \epsilon \leq \|\mathcal{S}f_\epsilon^{\alpha-1} - \ell_\epsilon\|_{L^2(\Omega)}. \tag{4.14}$$

where $\kappa > 1$ is a constant.

Theorem 4.3. *Let assume the a priori condition (3.1), and the noise assumption (1.2) hold, and the regularization parameter choice α is chosen by discrepancy principle (4.14). Then we have the convergent estimate:*

$$\|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \text{ is of order } \epsilon^{\frac{s}{s+1}}. \tag{4.15}$$

Proof. Using the triangle inequality, we get

$$\|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f^\alpha\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + \|f^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)}. \tag{4.16}$$

We firstly give an estimate \mathcal{I}_2 , we can obtain the boundness of \mathcal{I}_2 by estimating $\|\mathcal{S}(f^\alpha - f)\|_{L^2(\Omega)}$ and $\|f^\alpha - f\|_{\mathbb{H}^{2s}(\Omega)}$. From (4.4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{S}(f^\alpha - f)\|_{L^2(\Omega)} &= \left\| \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) \langle \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(\cdot) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &\leq \left\| \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) \langle \ell - \ell_\epsilon \rangle e_m(\cdot) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + \left\| \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) \langle \ell_\epsilon, e_m \rangle e_m(\cdot) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &\leq \epsilon \mathcal{A}_3 + \kappa \epsilon = (\mathcal{A}_3 + \kappa) \epsilon. \end{aligned} \tag{4.17}$$

Applying the a priori bound condition for f , it gives

$$\|f^\alpha - f\|_{\mathbb{H}^{2s}(\Omega)} = \left\| \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \theta_\alpha(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) (\lambda_m^2)^{2s} \frac{\langle \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(\cdot)}{\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi(\tau) d\tau \right) dt} \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \mathcal{M}. \tag{4.18}$$

By using the Lemma 2.4 and Theorem 3.1, (4.18) becomes

$$\|f^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \left(T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1} \right)^{\frac{-s}{s+1}} \left(\frac{\mathcal{A}_3 + \kappa}{\rho \mathcal{A}_1} \right)^{\frac{s}{s+1}} \mathcal{M}^{\frac{1}{s+1}} \epsilon^{\frac{s}{s+1}}. \tag{4.19}$$

From (4.14), for $s > 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa\epsilon &\leq \left\| \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \theta_{\alpha-1}(\mu_m) \langle \ell_\epsilon, e_m \rangle e_m(\cdot) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &\leq \left\| \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \theta_{\alpha-1}(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) \langle \ell_\epsilon - \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(\cdot) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} + \left\| \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \theta_{\alpha-1}(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) \langle \ell, e_m \rangle e_m(\cdot) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \\ &\leq \epsilon + \left\| \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \theta_{\alpha-1}(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) \langle f, e_m \rangle \rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi_\epsilon(\tau) d\tau \right) dt e_m(\cdot) \right\|_{L^2(\Omega)}, \end{aligned} \tag{4.20}$$

Because of relationship between $\mu_{\epsilon,m}$ and $\mathcal{Z}_{\epsilon,m}(\rho, t, T, \Phi_\epsilon)$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa\epsilon &\leq \epsilon + \mathcal{M} \sup_{m \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{\theta_{\alpha-1}(\mu_{\epsilon,m})}{(\lambda_m^2)^s} |k\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi_\epsilon(\tau) d\tau \right) dt|^{1+s} \\ &\quad \times |k\rho \int_0^T \left(\int_0^t e^{\lambda_m(\tau-t)} (t-\tau) \Phi_\epsilon(\tau) d\tau \right) dt|^{-s}, \\ &\leq \epsilon + \frac{\mathcal{M}}{\lambda_1^{2s}} \frac{1}{k^{1+s} \rho^s} \sup_{m \in \mathbb{N}} \theta_{\alpha-1}(\mu_{\epsilon,m}) |\mu_{\epsilon,m}|^{1+s} \\ &\leq \epsilon + \frac{\mathcal{M}}{\lambda_1^{2s} \rho^s} \left(\frac{2}{\mathcal{A}_2} \right)^s \left(T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1} \right)^{-s} \Theta_{1+s} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha k} \right)^{1+s}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.21}$$

This implies that

$$\alpha k \leq \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_1 \rho \mathcal{A}_2} \right)^{\frac{s}{s+1}} \left(T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1} \right)^{-\frac{s}{s+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\kappa - 1} \right)^{\frac{1}{s+1}} \left(\frac{\mathcal{M}}{\epsilon} \right)^{\frac{1}{1+s}}. \tag{4.22}$$

Similar to (4.8), it gives

$$\|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f^\alpha\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \epsilon \mathcal{A}_3 \alpha k. \tag{4.23}$$

Substituting (4.22) into (4.23), we find that

$$\|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f^\alpha\|_{L^2(\Omega)} \leq \epsilon^{\frac{s}{1+s}} \mathcal{M}^{\frac{1}{1+s}} \mathcal{A}_3 \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_1 \rho \mathcal{A}_2} \right)^{\frac{s}{s+1}} \left(T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1} \right)^{-\frac{s}{s+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\kappa - 1} \right)^{\frac{1}{s+1}}. \tag{4.24}$$

Combining (4.19) to (4.24), we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \|f_\epsilon^\alpha - f\|_{L^2(\Omega)} &\leq \epsilon^{\frac{s}{1+s}} \mathcal{M}^{\frac{1}{1+s}} \left(\mathcal{A}_3 \left(\frac{2}{\lambda_1 \rho \mathcal{A}_2} \right)^{\frac{s}{s+1}} \left(T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1} \right)^{-\frac{s}{s+1}} \left(\frac{1}{\kappa - 1} \right)^{\frac{1}{s+1}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(T - \frac{2}{\lambda_1} \right)^{-\frac{s}{s+1}} \left(\frac{\mathcal{A}_3 + \kappa}{\rho \mathcal{A}_1} \right)^{\frac{s}{s+1}} \right). \end{aligned} \tag{4.25}$$

□

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References

- [1] V.M. Bulavatsky, fractional differential analog of biparabolic evolution equation and some its applications, *Cybern Syst Anal.* September 2016;52(5):737–747.
- [2] V.M. Bulavatsky, Some nonlocal boundary-Value problems for the biparabolic evolution equation and its fractional-Differential analog, *Cybern Syst Anal.* September 2019;55(5):796–804.
- [3] Y.J. Deng, Z.H. Liu, L. Youjun, Zhenhai, Iteration methods on sideways parabolic equations, *Inverse Problems* 25 (2009), no. 9, 095004, 14 pp.
- [4] V.L. Fushchich, A.S. Galitsyn, A.S. Polubinskii, A new mathematical model of heat conduction processes, *Ukr Math J.* 1990;42:210–216.
- [5] G. Fichera, Is the Fourier theory of heat propagation paradoxical. *Rendiconti Del Circolo Matematico Di Palermo?*. 1992;41:5–28.
- [6] N.N. Hung, H.D. Binh, N.H. Luc, N.T.K. An, L.D. Long, *Stochastic sub-diffusion equation with conformable derivative driven by standard Brownian motion*, *Advances in the Theory of Nonlinear Analysis and its Applications* 5 (2021) No. 3, 287–299.
- [7] L.N. Huynh, N.H. Luc, D. Baleanu and L.D. Long, Recovering the space source term for the fractional-diffusion equation with Caputo-Fabrizio derivative. *J. Inequal. Appl.* 2021, Paper No. 28, 20 pp.
- [8] L. Joseph, D.D. Preziosi, Heat waves. *Rev Mod Phys.* 1989;61:41–73. DOI:10.1103/revmodphys.61.41
- [9] V.A. Kozlov and V.G. Mazya, *On iterative procedures for solving ill-posed boundary value problems that preserve differential equations*, *Leningrad Mathematics Journal*, vol.1, pp. 1207-1228, 1990.
- [10] N.H. Luc, D. Baleanu, L.D. Long, and N.H. Can, Reconstructing the right-hand side of a fractional subdiffusion equation from the final data. *J. Inequal. Appl.* 2020, Paper No. 53, 15 pp.
- [11] N.H. Luc, D. Baleanu, R.P. Agarwal, L.D. Long, Identifying the source function for time fractional diffusion with non-local in time conditions. *Comput. Appl. Math.* 40 (2021), no. 5, Paper No. 159, 21 pp.
- [12] D.H.Q. Nam, L.D. Long, D. O'Regan, T.B. Ngoc, N.H. Tuan, Identification of the right-hand side in a bi-parabolic equation with final data, *Appl. Anal.* 101 (2022), no. 4, 1157–1175.
- [13] B.D. Nghia, N.H. Luc, H.D. Binh, L.D. Long, Regularization method for the problem of determining the source function using integral conditions, *Advances in the Theory of Nonlinear Analysis and its Applications* 5 (2021) No. 3, 351–362.
- [14] N.H. Tuan, M. Kirane, L.D. Long, N.V. Thinh: Filter regularization for an inverse parabolic problem in several variables, *Electron. J. Differential Equations*, Paper No. 24 (2016), 13 pp.
- [15] J.G. Wang, T. Wei, An iterative method for backward time-fractional diffusion problem, *Numer Methods Partial Differ Equ.* 2014;30(6):2029–2041.
- [16] T. Wei, X.L. Li, Y.S. Li, An inverse time-dependent source problem for a time-fractional diffusion equation, *Inverse Prob.* 2016;32(8):085003.
- [17] T. Wei, Z.Q. Zhang, Reconstruction of a time-dependent source term in a time-fractional diffusion equation, *Eng Anal Boundary Ele.* 2013;37(1):23–31.
- [18] F. Yang, C.L. Fu, X.X. Li, The inverse source problem for time-fractional diffusion equation: stability analysis and regularization, *Inverse Prob Sci Eng.* 2015;23(6):969–996.
- [19] F. Yang, C.L. Fu, The quasi-reversibility regularization method for identifying the unknown source for time fractional diffusion equation, *Appl Math Model.* 2015;39(5):1500–1512
- [20] F. Zouyed, S. Djemoui, An iterative regularization method for identifying the source term in a second order differential equation, *Math. Probl. Eng.* 2015, Art. ID 713403, 9 pp.